

De-sexualising Identities: Codes of Resistance in Tanuja Desai Hidier's *Born Confused*

Dr Narinder K. Sharma

Assistant Professor

Department of English, Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, Punjab

Abstract

*The article explores the representations of lesbianism and transgender as ways of challenging sexual codes, signifying an act of resistance to subvert the systems of normative heterosexuality. Accordingly, lesbian (or gay) analysis seeks to unearth concealed resistances by focussing on the complex networks of bond between women, with special references to narratives that involve same-sex relationships or other forms of sexual representation to restructure or reclaim identities that have otherwise been marginalised by dominant power structures. Tanuja Desai Hidier's novel *Born Confused* (2002) presents the problematics and possibilities of such a bond between female characters, who employ their relationships as a method of addressing uneven power dynamics within the context of teenage American culture. Additionally, the presence of a transsexual character in this novel, who violates standard gender conventions, further complicates and opposes set social categories, providing a closer assessment of gender and sexuality, highlighting a transgressive approach to redefining the normative order, and demonstrating how queer identities could pave the way for an authentic existence.*

Keywords: Lesbianism, Resistance, Networks, Power, Gender, Sexuality

Feminism, as a critical code for identifying women-centric issues and representations in any literary exercise, has been an important discourse as it highlights women's experiences as opposed to male discursive practices. Accordingly, feminist criticism deals with female-centric characters and situations in literary works and emphasises the phallogocentric nature of language, which prioritizes phallus and masculinity. This discourse also has a political dimension; it argues that a woman is not biologically a woman but rather becomes one as a result of society's patriarchal hegemony and male-dominated social superstructure. In the 1990s, feminist philosophical contributions fostered the growth of a new gender-based literary interpretation, fostering a novel type of intellectual inquiry. It emphasised that gender "...is not something that one is; it is something one does—an act...a 'doing' rather than a 'being'" (Butler 25). This kind of gender criticism flourished as a theory of resistance in the realm of literature, such as feminism, and acquired some of its visible traits as rebellion, known as lesbian and gay theory, and later queer

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024

A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

theory, which emerged from feminist pronouncements. However, it later achieved disciplinary independence because of its unique perspectives on the issues of sexuality and subjectivity. While feminism focuses on the binary oppositions and codes that destabilize and malign women's discourse, practitioners and proponents of lesbian and gay criticism emphasize atypical sexual orientation and preferences as the basis for critical interpretation of a specific literary phenomenon. Therefore, lesbian and gay criticism offers a fresh perspective on the text, which was previously assessed using the principles of feminism and similar theoretical exercises within the context of gender studies.

Lesbian and gay critics have concentrated on textual depictions and interpretations related to the concerns of homosexuality and heterosexuality. They also diverge from essentialist feminist ideas, which view gender or sexuality—male and female—as innate and intrinsic, natural occurrences. By contrast, lesbian and gay critiques embrace constructionist principles, viewing gender and sexuality as sociocultural constructs. Rich opines, "Heterosexuality has been both forcibly and subliminally imposed on women...It is the great lie of our civilization, sustained by the domination of male interests" (642). Thus, lesbian and gay critics challenge the simplistic essentialism of feminist critics, who maintain that a universal female identity exists regardless of racial, class, or sexual orientation differences. In this sense, lesbian and gay criticism, particularly that of lesbians, specifically targets the practices of heterosexuality and highlights how they are often taken for granted and how they oppress female identity, thereby limiting the choices and inclinations of women in matters of sexual contentment.

According to literary works, lesbianism is typically portrayed as a violation of traditional sexual norms, and women's engagement in this behavior is often seen as an attempt to subvert and weaken patriarchal control and moral standards. This is because lesbianism rejects different ways of working with patriarchal exploitation and instead focuses on relationships between women, which, by definition, are a form of resistance to and a radical reorganization of existing social relationships. Therefore, lesbian (or gay) criticism aims to uncover hidden forms of resistance in narratives, such as relationships between individuals of the same sex or other forms of sexual experimentation, in an attempt to reposition their identities that have been subjugated by existing

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024

A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

power structures. Foucault opines, “Where there is power, there is resistance, and yet, or rather consequently, this resistance is never in a position of exteriority in relation to power” (95). In this paper, the narrative being examined is Tanuja Desai Hidier's novel *Born Confused* (2002), which portrays the interactions between several female characters who use their typical female bond as a weapon to challenge unequal power dynamics among teenage Americans. Specifically, the novel features two types of bonds: one is a close friendship between girls, while the other is a sexual or lesbian relationship between them. Additionally, the story includes a transvestite character who intentionally defies traditional gender norms by shifting between male and female identities, thereby resisting fixed categories of social relations.

Born Confused is the story of Dimple Lala, a seventeen-year-old girl who is struggling with the culture she belongs to and how she sees herself. Dimple, an Indian-American girl, is the daughter of Dr. Rohit Lala, a Gujrati economic migrant, and Shilpa Lala, a housewife. As expatriates, the Lalas are deeply engrossed in the problematics of their lost homeland and Indian culture, which they diligently preserve at home through the numerous souvenirs of India and their participation in all the rituals and ceremonies intrinsic to the culture. In this context, Dimple perceives herself as both too American to blend into Indian society and too Indian to gain acceptance as an American. She has been confused about her identity, as she could remember. Shilpa, the mother, expects her daughter to fall in love with this cultural clash, but Dimple, being born and bred in America, finds it nearly impossible to admire. The protagonist thinks, “My mother always got carried away when she shopped in India...it seemed she was trying to bring back the whole country with her in the suitcase” (Hidier 36).

The defining aspect of Dimple's life is her best friend, Gwendolyn (Gywn), an American girl with wrecked-home antecedents. What she longs for is family, as is visible in Dimple's perfect family portrait. Interestingly, Dimple is the embodiment of American beauty in all respects and seeks equality in all walks of life. The manner in which she interacts with Gywn lends this narrative its special character because it constitutes the site for female-female relationships, particularly within the context of the American sociocultural environment. At the same time, Gywn and Dimple's relationship experiences numerous ups and downs due to various issues, ultimately

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024

A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

leading to reconciliation after a prolonged period of separation. The relationship serves as a means for individuals to express their subjectivities vis-à-vis the intricate network of normative checks and balances that challenge their existence. Interestingly, the narrative has an intricate structure because it contains a subplot involving Kavita, Dimple's cousin, and her girlfriend Sabina, who live together before peacefully separating consensually. There is also Zara, a transvestite, an Indian (man) in America who presents as a woman on account of his unique sexual preferences. Importantly, Dimple achieves an authentic vision through her experiences and interactions with these characters, who inspire her to embrace her dual identity as Indian and American, both of which are unique and possess the potential to explore the endless possibilities inherent in this rainbow existence. In this sense, the protagonist carves her identity through the interplay of sexualities and their potential to challenge society's normative structure.

Before proceeding further, it is imperative that Dimple and Gywn's relationship be subjected to a deeper analysis. As already stated, the protagonist's suppression of her Indian identity is evident in the narrative. Her parents, being hardcore *desis*, expect their daughter, a second-generation immigrant, to adhere to their Indian ways and customs, a fact Dimple is unaware of despite holding an American passport. On one occasion when Dimple returns home inebriated, Dimple's mother regrets their decision to come to America, losing their daughter to the diabolic culture of satyrs. However, the burden of upholding her rich ancestral culture is too great for Dimple to bear, and this is what makes her get into conundrums as to what she is—Indian or American. The novel's first page encapsulates the protagonist's duality, as she ponders her perplexing mental state and uncertain identity:

I guess the whole mess started around my birthday. Amendment: my first birthday. I was born turned around, and apparently, I was holding my head in such a way that resulted in twelve treacherous hours of painful labor for my mother to eject me...Born backwards and clueless. In other words, I was born confused. So, I came the wrong way. And I have been getting it all wrong ever since. (Hildier 1)

Such a clinical estimate of her birth and subjectivity hints at her utterly confused sense of being. At another juncture, we witness her grappling with the dual identity of Indian-American: "So, not quite Indian, and not quite American. Usually, I felt more along the lines of Alien" (Hildier 13). Following this quintessential Indian parenting pattern, Lalas instills the notion of a suitable boy in

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024

A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

her mind as she approaches maturity. Rubin opines, “Every society... has a sex/gender system—a set of arrangements by which the biological raw material of human sex and procreation is shaped by human social intervention” (159). Accordingly, a severely insensible atmosphere at home draws Dimple instinctively towards Gywn, the epitome of American beauty and autonomy. Because of her friendship with Gywn, the protagonist finds new meaning in her dazed life. This friendship renders Dimple something else too, which her ‘otherness’ as an Indian-origin girl longs for—that is, a delusional oneness with the Americans who, according to her own theory, otherwise could have marginalized her. Being with Gywn also signifies that Dimple could feel as if she were an American, setting her apart from her parents' mystifying and exotic orientalism. Gywn’s prototypical American way of dressing, her candidness in dating games, her casualness about physical intimacy, and her normalcy with drugs catches Dimple’s fancy. Gywn's unrestrained lifestyle represents freedom for Dimple, a lifestyle that her parents despise and refuse to grant her. On the other hand, Gywn also relishes Dimple's company because of her idyllic family of loving and caring parents, an experience that Gywn was deprived of due to her parents' divorce. She is with her mother, for whom Gywn is not a priority or responsibility, and she has no intention of monitoring or correcting her daughter's misbehavior. This uninviting familial background draws her to Dimple and her family.

The origins of their exceptional rapport are grounded in several tangible factors. For one, Dimple holds an infatuation and fascination for Gywn, stemming from her dual marginalized status as a woman and a member of an exotic cultural group. Notably, the tendency towards same-sex attraction or an intense fixation on another woman often arises from a perception of subjugation within a male-dominated societal framework. In this way, the union of two women in a close relationship is an escape from the codes of normative morality. Women must “...write through their bodies, they must invent the impregnable language that will wreck partitions, classes, and rhetorics, regulations, and codes” (Cixous 886). In this sense, their yearning for each other's companionship, despite facing rejection and silence from their parents for various reasons, suggests a subtle form of togetherness that transgresses gender space. Notably, Dimple and Gywn display theoretical lesbianism in the form of spiritual solace in times of distress, but there are also hints of physical passion, as Dimple appears to harbor a fetish for Gywn's perfectly sculpted

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024

A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

curvaceous body. Unlike her plump and chubby physiology, Gywn is skinny and has a titillating character. Compared with Gywn, Dimple is negatively self-conscious of her unattractive physical appearance. The author's depiction of the girls' physical features, as portrayed from their individual viewpoints, implies a rejection of the world that has failed them. Acknowledging that heterosexuality is not the only means for girls to express their concealed dissatisfaction prompts both Dimple and Gwyn to subvert the fixed signifiers of essentialist sexuality, signifying the possibilities reinscribing gender and sexuality.

Dimple's obsession with Gywn also symbolises the latter's being the emblem of Americanism, which Dimple desires to embody because her ethnic identity prevents her from fully assimilating into the dominant culture and keeps her in a liminal position. In addition, the double marginalisation of being an outsider and a woman attracts her towards Gywn. Through this friendship, she approximates the American way of life, and her free-flowing sexuality empowers her to navigate the slanted social superstructure. Consequently, the ways in which Gywn enslaves men are important lessons that Dimple enjoys learning, and such a devious use of female sexuality is interpreted as power by Dimple. Further, Gywn's fetish for Dimple stems from her inadequate family circumstances. Her divorced parents care little for her, leaving her in dire need of familial love. Her typical American upbringing exposes her to perverted boyfriends, who are obsessed with carnal desires. She goes from one failed heterosexual relationship to another to find peace in Dimple's company. In Dimple's company, she experiences a fulfilment that is missing in her entire life. She also finds Dimple virginity and sexual turpitude. Thus, she allows Dimple's fixed female identity to transform into a fluid one shaped by her own imagination in a bid to challenge the infidelity of masculine sexuality. It highlights a fluid notion of identity, where constant switching among a range of different roles and positions makes Gywn feel somewhat comfortable. On a critical note, the voluntary blurring of gender identities is the tool with which both Gywn and Dimple seem to transgress unfavorable social superstructures and relationships.

Another transgression of normative sexual codes in the narrative relates to lesbianism and sexual bonding between women, which can be seen as a result of the radicalization of sexual behavior dictated by cultural practices. Unlike the relationship between Dimple and Gywn, this

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024

A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

relationship is explicitly lesbian, with its audacity and unabashed declaration leading to the ostracization and ignominy of its practitioners who attempt to transcend the boundaries of sexual ethics. The novelist depicts Kavita's relationship with Sabina, a typical American youth, and her cousin Dimple through a subplot. Kavita travels to the United States from India to pursue higher education, coming from a conservative Gujarati family. Despite her family's orthodox background, Kavita embraces her queer identity, a decision that can be seen as a form of resistance against societal norms. According to Rich, this act represents the lesbian continuum, a critique of single-dimensional feminism that recognizes the complex and intimate nature of women's experiences. Kavita's decision to embrace her queer tendencies also sets her apart from oppressed females in her family, reflecting her determination to overcome her unprivileged status. Rich opines: "I mean the term lesbian continuum to include a range—through each woman's life and throughout history—of woman-identified experience, not simply the fact that a woman has had or consciously desired genital sexual experience with another woman" (184). This woman continuum translates itself as envisaging a forum to bring forth discriminating practices directed against women not only by male authority but also by heterosexual womanhood. Kavita's choice supports Rich's definition of the lesbian continuum, suggesting potential interconnections for women to bond together. Kavita employs this continuum to assert her sexual choice, transgressing the prevailing norm of heterosexuality. In her endeavors to legitimize lesbianism in her expatriate community, she effectively deprives it of its sexual connotations and transforms it into a political act, thereby creating something novel. Even following the dissolution of her partnership with Sabina, Kavita maintains a resolute demeanor to allow her continuum to persist while pursuing a fresh, unconventional partner who shares her unorthodox inclinations. It highlights her steadfast dedication to resisting the normative heterosexual identity.

Further, Zara, a transvestite or drag queen in the novel, represents another type of transgression of the normative regimes of heterosexuality and homosexuality in the narrative as "...queer orientations... involve disorientation; one loses one's sense of direction because one's point of view does not line up with the lines that are supposed to direct one" (Ahmed 565). Zara is a noteworthy example of the fluidity of sexual identity, as it presents gender as a structure of differences without any fixed meanings. From an essentialist perspective, transvestitism is

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024

A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

considered an abnormality, characterizing a transvestite as an individual who derives sexual pleasure from dressing in clothes of the opposite sex and adopting queer behaviors. LGBTIQ critics examine this position in the context of gay and lesbian choices and opine that identity is a complex combination of chosen allegiances, social positions, and professional roles rather than a fixed inner essence, signifying gender hybridity. After her friendship with Gywn ends, Dimple meets Zara in an Indian assembly of young people, and she is impressed by Zara's elegance, only to be shocked to learn that Zara is actually a man. Zara narrates how he fled from India due to his unique preferences and ultimately found refuge in America. Interestingly, his fluidic identification with the identities, sometimes his and sometimes her, is restrained by outward sociocultural pressures. However, he chooses to transcend such barriers and tells Dimple: “Believe it or not, Dimple—and I would believe it—I am just a regular person who has decided to be who I am in life. That’s all” (Hildier 442). Zara’s candid views about maintaining identity help Dimple reinvent herself. She learns that it is a person's attitude that shapes identity, not external factors. When Dimple's photographs appear in a New York magazine, she experiences a profound sense of accomplishment and recognition as an artist: Zara's games with his body and personality attest to the fact that a person’s potential for refashioning oneself is dependent on one’s will, and this is how Dimple is able to milk the benefits out of her own hybridity. Accordingly, she employs her hybridity to reconstitute herself, repurpose the received ideas, and subvert the dualistic frameworks to unveil the boundless possibilities of the human form and existence.

In this broader context, *Born Confused* introduces readers to a diverse array of characters who deliberately subvert societal norms, such as those related to sexual relations and marriage, to achieve a sense of integration in life. Their purposeful acts of iconoclasm represent a transgressive approach to redefining the normative order, demonstrating that their queer identities pave the way for an authentic existence. The analysis clearly shows that both Kavita and Zara, although tormented by the asphyxiating forces of patriarchy and societal fundamentalism, ultimately find liberation through their acts of transgression. The depiction of the central character's epiphany, influenced by interactions with lesbians and gays, underscores the cutting-edge insight and unapologetically bold analysis that characterize the new generation of novelists as they navigate and redefine contemporary relational discourse.

LITCULT:

A Journal of Literary and Cultural Discourse, Vol 01, No. 1, Nov 2024
A Peer Reviewed Open Access e-Journal

Works Cited

Ahmed, Sara. *Queer Phenomenology: Orientations, Objects, Others*. Duke University Press, 2006.

Butler, Judith. *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*. Routledge, 1990.

Cixous, Hélène. "The Laugh of the Medusa." *Signs*, vol. 1, no. 4, 1976, pp. 875-893.

Foucault, Michel. *The History of Sexuality, Volume 1: An Introduction*. Translated by Robert Hurley, Vintage Books, 1990.

Hidier, Tanuja Desai. *Born Confused*. New York: Penguin Books, 2002.

Rich, Adrienne. "Compulsory Heterosexuality and Lesbian Existence." *Signs*, vol. 5, no. 4, 1980, pp. 631-660.

_____. "Contemporary Heterosexuality and Lesbian Existence." *Blood, Bread, and Poetry: Selected Prose*. Birmingham: Virago, 1987, pp. 174-192.

Rubin, Gayle. "The Traffic in Women: Notes on the 'Political Economy' of Sex." *Toward an Anthropology of Women*, edited by Rayna R. Reiter, Monthly Review Press, 1975, pp. 157-210.

Corresponding Author: Narinder K. Sharma (Email: narinderksharma.elt@gmail.com)